

Reporting checklist for genetic association study.

Based on the STREGA guidelines.

Instructions to authors

Complete this checklist by entering the page numbers from your manuscript where readers will find each of the items listed below.

Your article may not currently address all the items on the checklist. Please modify your text to include the missing information. If you are certain that an item does not apply, please write "n/a" and provide a short explanation.

Upload your completed checklist as an extra file when you submit to a journal.

In your methods section, say that you used the STREGA reporting guidelines, and cite them as:

Little J, Higgins JP, Ioannidis JP, Moher D, Gagnon F, von Elm E, Khoury MJ, Cohen B, Davey-Smith G, Grimshaw J, Scheet P, Gwinn M, Williamson RE, Zou GY, Hutchings K, Johnson CY, Tait V, Wiens M, Golding J, van Duijn C, McLaughlin J, Paterson A, Wells G, Fortier I, Freedman M, Zecevic M, King R, Infante-Rivard C, Stewart A, Birkett N; STrengthening the REporting of Genetic Association Studies. STrengthening the REporting of Genetic Association Studies (STREGA): An Extension of the STROBE Statement.

		Reporting Item	Page Number
Title and abstract			
Title	#1a	Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Title
Abstract	#1b	Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	
Background/rationale			
	#2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Introduction Sections 1-3
Objectives			
	#3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses. State if the study is the first report of a genetic association, a replication effort, or both.	Introduction Section 4
Study design			
	#4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Methods Section 2.1
Setting			
	#5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment,	Methods

		exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Section 2.2
Eligibility criteria			
	#6a	Cohort study – Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Describe methods of follow-up. Case-control study – Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of case ascertainment and control selection. Give the rationale for the choice of cases and controls. Cross-sectional study – Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Give information on the criteria and methods for selection of subsets of participants from a larger study, when relevant.	Methods Sections 2.3,2.4
	#6b	Cohort study – For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed. Case-control study – For matched studies, give matching criteria and the number of controls per case.	NA
Variables			
	#7a	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Methods Sections 2.1, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8
	#7b	Clearly define genetic exposures (genetic variants) using a widely-used nomenclature system. Identify variables likely to be associated with population stratification (confounding by ethnic origin).	Methods Section 2.11,2.12
Data sources/measurement			
	#8a	For each variable of interest give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable.	Methods Section 2.10 – 2.12
	#8b	Describe laboratory methods, including source and storage of DNA, genotyping methods and platforms (including the allele calling algorithm used, and its version), error rates and call rates. State the laboratory / centre where genotyping was done. Describe comparability of laboratory methods if there is more than one group. Specify whether genotypes were assigned using all of the data from the study simultaneously or in smaller batches.	Methods Section 2.10 – 2.12
Bias			
	#9a	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Discussion Section 4.1
	#9b	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Discussion Section 4.1
Study size			
	#10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	Methods Section 2.9
Quantitative variables			
	#11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen, and why. If applicable, describe how effects of treatment were dealt with.	Methods Section 2.13
Statistical methods			

	#12a	Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding. State software version used and options (or settings) chosen.	Methods Section 2.13
	#12b	Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Methods Section 2.13
	#12c	Explain how missing data were addressed	NA
	#12d	If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed	NA
	#12e	Describe any sensitivity analyses	Methods Section 2.13
	#12f	State whether Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium was considered and, if so, how.	Methods Section 2.13
	#12g	Describe any methods used for inferring genotypes or haplotypes	Methods Section 2.13
	#12h	Describe any methods used to assess or address population stratification.	Methods Section 2.13
	#12i	Describe any methods used to address multiple comparisons or to control risk of false positive findings.	Methods Section 2.13
	#12j	Describe any methods used to address and correct for relatedness among subjects	Methods Section 2.13
Participants			
	#13a	Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable. Report numbers of individuals in whom genotyping was attempted and numbers of individuals in whom genotyping was successful.	Methods Section 2.1 Results Table 4
	#13b	Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	NA
	#13c	Consider use of a flow diagram	NA
Descriptive data			
	#14a	Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable. Consider giving information by genotype	Results Section 1 Table 4
	#14b	Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	NA
	#14c	Cohort study – Summarize follow-up time, e.g. average and total amount.	NA
Outcome data			
	#15	Cross-sectional study – Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable. Report outcomes (phenotypes) for each genotype category	Table 4
Main results			
	#16a	Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	Tables 5 - 8
	#16b	Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	NA

	#16c	If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	Tables 5-8
	#16d	Report results of any adjustments for multiple comparisons	Table 8
Other analyses			
	#17a	Report other analyses done—e.g., analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	Table 7,8
	#17b	Report other analyses done—e.g., analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	Table 7,8
	#17c	Report other analyses done—e.g., analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	Table 7,8
Key results			
	#18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Discussion Sections 3, and 4
Limitations			
	#19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias.	Discussion Section 4.1
Interpretation			
	#20	Give a cautious overall interpretation considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence.	Conclusion
Generalisability			
	#21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Discussion Section 5 - 8
Funding			
	#22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	Funding

None The STREGA checklist is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY. This checklist can be completed online using <https://www.goodreports.org/>, a tool made by the [EQUATOR Network](#) in collaboration with [Penelope.ai](#)